

Summary of the March 14, 2023 Webinar, “Digital Storytelling in the Global South”

<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/neh-ahrc-digital-storytelling-webinar/>

Report prepared by Carla Klehm and Rosie Campbell

March 31, 2023

This report is associated with the “Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms: A Model to Empower Education Initiatives Across the Global South.” This was a 2022-2023 Foundations-level (Level I) AHRC grant in the UK-US Digital Scholarship in Cultural Institutions programme, in collaboration with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH, HND-284967-22), awarded jointly to the University of Cambridge (Dr. Stefania Merlo, PI) and University of Arkansas (Dr. Carla Klehm, PI).

Summary

As part of the “*Digital Storytelling on African Urbanism*” project, PIs Klehm and Merlo organized a virtual seminar on digital storytelling in low-resourced educational environments in the Global South. Hosted by the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research at the University of Cambridge, the webinar sought to benefit US and UK institutions, and scholars and institutions across the Global South who are also working to address digital-enabled equitable participation. Titled, “Digital Storytelling in the Global South: Utilizing Spatial Archives for Diverse Audiences,” the webinar explored how archaeologists, historians, museum experts, and educators can engage with emerging digital technologies to explore the past alongside the public. The webinar took place on March 14, 2023, over the course of three hours.

“Digital Storytelling in the Global South” brings together experts in archaeology and beyond to discuss three themes:

1. Storytelling with spatial archives, on how various forms of spatial data can be incorporated into and structured within archival databases for digital storytelling;
2. Digital infrastructure in low-resourced environments, on the logistical challenges with connecting audiences with varying technical competencies, computer and internet speeds, and cultural understandings and language barriers to resources associated with digital publication;
3. Digital storytelling and the narrative voice, on how marginalized voices and perspectives can be integrated into digital storytelling process, empowering communities to engage with storytelling in self-directed, generative ways that deepen connections to cultural heritage.

Each theme is an hour in length, with time dedicated equally to presentation and audience participation. The flyer advertisement that was circulated is included at the end of this report.

A primary objective of the webinar was to bring together a range of scholars from a variety of disciplines across the digital humanities. In our earlier survey of other digital storytelling and archival initiatives, we had recognized a siloing of examples and dialogues that paralleled

traditional academic disciplines: archaeologists tended to talk to other archaeologists, historians to other historians, etc., even though important projects were emerging in geography, information sciences, and even engineering. Part of our recruitment effort, then, included:

- Featuring projects based in the Global South, as these tend to not have as widespread international attention (and funding support) as their Global North counterparts;
- Promoting leadership by underrepresented scholars;
- Fostering a multidisciplinary conversation, where fields of expertise range, and a variety of universities, museums, and non-profits could share their comparative efforts;
- Highlighting research on African and African American prehistory, history, and culture.

The final list of 13 subject matter experts included:

Anton Coetzee (School of Arts, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa)

Angelia Payne (Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies, University of Arkansas)

Siddique Motala (Centre for Research in Engineering Education, University of Cape Town, South Africa)

David Wallace (School of Information, University of Michigan)

Edward Gonzalez-Tennant (Anthropology, University of Texas-RGV)

Don Lafreniere (Geography and GIS, Michigan Technological University)

Hussein Suleman (Computer Science Department, University of Cape Town)

Azadeh Vafadari (McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research, University of Cambridge)

Justine Wintjes (Kwa Zulu Natal Museum, South Africa)

Amanda Esterhuysen (Origins Center, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa)

Daniela Gachago (Center for Innovation in Learning and Teaching, University of Cape Town, South Africa)

Noor Niefertagdien (History Workshop, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa)

Mutau Kyanya (African Digital Heritage, Nairobi, Kenya)

The webinar was facilitated by the project PIs, Carla Klehm (US) and Stefania Merlo (UK).

The webinar was recorded for open-access publication online, with the consent of the participants. The webinar recordings are available on the *metsemegologolo* website, at <https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/neh-ahrc-digital-storytelling-webinar/>. The videos are divided into three sessions that follow the session presentations and discussions on each of the three topics (storytelling with spatial data, digital infrastructure in low-resource environments, and digital storytelling and the narrating voice).

Analytics

As part of assessing the impact of our webinar recruitment and attendance, we conducted an analysis of the website traffic from the *Metsemegologolo* website before and after the circulation of the webinar flyer, and during and after the webinar. Data was gathered using a WPStatistics Wordpress plugin.

Following the circulation of the webinar flyer on March 8th, there were 612 visits to the website, from 249 unique visitors. There was a clear spike in website traffic attributed to this circulation.

In the 30 days leading up to the event the *metsemegologolo* website had 676 visitors, meaning 38% of these were related to event circulation. There were 229 registrations for the webinar.

During the webinar, there were 167 participants (127 unique). While some people logged in for specific sessions or presentations, only 12 users stayed for less than 40 minutes. Approximately half of the users were based in Africa. Overall, the project team was impressed by the strong interest among the digital humanities community that these topics and this format generated, especially for engaging with audiences in the Global South.

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